

High-Resolution Digital Terrain Model on a sample area of the Italian national territory

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¹ *Abstract*— This study presents the development of a high-resolution (5 m) digital terrain model (DTM) for Italy, prepared within the PNRR project “National Centre for HPC, Big Data and Quantum Computing”. The goal is to enhance the accuracy of national-scale elevation data, improving upon the existing dataset TINITALY, originally at 10 m spatial resolution across Italy, by integrating sparse but extensive multi-source LiDAR data.

A key challenge is the heterogeneous and fragmented distribution of LiDAR datasets, acquired by different institutions at different times, with varying resolutions, and different coordinate reference systems (CRS). To address this, a structured database has been designed to allow efficient updates as new LiDAR data become available. The methodology combines high-performance computing infrastructure with open-source software, leveraging GRASS GIS, Linux shell scripts, and data-parallel workflows to process large-scale datasets.

The data processing pipeline includes automated data processing, including CRS harmonization and mosaicking, ensuring a seamless and homogeneous national DTM. TINITALY data were interpolated to 5 m to bridge LiDAR gaps, prioritizing data recency and resolution in overlapping areas. The workflow was tested on a sample area with complex topography, validating the feasibility of the approach and ensuring data consistency across diverse terrains.

The final product is a high-accuracy DTM, suitable for hydrological and slope stability modeling, natural hazard assessment, and environmental management. This methodology, scalable and updatable, will provide a nationally consistent dataset, enabling analyses that were previously constrained by data fragmentation and resolution limitations.

I. INTRODUCTION

The increasing availability of high-resolution digital elevation models (DEMs) has revolutionized geomorphological, hydrological, and environmental analyses, enabling accurate terrain modeling [1]. However, merging data from different sources – such as airborne LiDAR, photogrammetric data, and satellite-based DEMs, with medium-resolution models like

TINITALY [2], [3], [4]– introduces significant challenges, including managing data discontinuities and ensuring smooth transitions between elevation models with different characteristics [5].

Several studies proposed advanced fusion methods to improve DEM consistency and accuracy [6], highlighting how variable-weighted approaches can significantly reduce vertical errors and enhance topographic representation. A systematic review by Ref. [5] identified key fusion techniques, including weighted averaging based on vertical errors and adaptive interpolation to reduce discontinuities between DEMs of different origins.

According to Ref. [7], in the Italian context, the availability of LiDAR data is limited to approximately 63% of the national territory, with many regions showing gaps in spatial coverage. This limitation presents a challenge in creating complete and accurate high-resolution DEMs.

The present study, developed within the frame of the PNRR project “National Centre for HPC, Big Data and Quantum Computing”, builds upon these findings and proposes an advanced methodology for high-resolution DEM fusion in Italy, by integrating LiDAR data from various sources and using the TINITALY elevation model to fill areas lacking high-resolution data.

The proposed approach consists of three main phases: data collection and pre-processing, DEM fusion using variable-weighted algorithms, and validation of the resulting elevation model. The effectiveness of this method was tested in a sample area in Emilia-Romagna (Northern Italy).

The final goal is to develop a coherent and accurate DEM, which is essential for environmental, hydrological, and land management applications. In fact, TINITALY is currently the highest-resolution DEM covering the whole of Italy, and is widely used by Italian researchers and practitioners, for a variety of applications [3]. The existence of such relatively high-resolution

DEM allows the consistent use across Italy of physically based models. For example, Refs.[8], [9] are example applications of a 3D rockfall model, Ref. [10] of a conceptual model for rapid-flow landslides, and Ref. [11] of an infinite slope stability model, though in a smaller area. We expect that the new DTM presented here will represent a great opportunity for improving similar applications in Italy.

II. DATA AND METHODS

A. Data description

The objective of this work is to establish a procedure for generating a high-resolution (HR) digital terrain model (DTM) for the Italian territory. This HR model was designed to enhance the resolution of TINITALY and ensure greater accuracy in elevation measurements through the integration of multiple LiDAR sources.

To achieve this, three primary types of digital elevation data were considered. The first consists of LiDAR data provided by the Ministry of the Environment and Energy Security (MEES), which covers the entire national territory and is available at 1m and 2m resolutions. These datasets are distributed directly from the MEES (<https://sim.mase.gov.it/portalediaccesso/mappe/#/viewer/new>) The second category includes LiDAR data from other institutions, such as regional administrations, municipalities, and Civil Protection agencies, which have the same resolution as the MEES data but may overlap or leave coverage gaps. The third dataset is TINITALY, a national-scale DEM with 10 m resolution, which is used to fill in gaps where LiDAR data are unavailable.

B. Merging procedure

The process of constructing the HR DTM consists of three phases: i) data collection and pre-processing, ii) data processing and merging, and iii) preliminary quality control.

1) Data collection and pre-processing

The first step involved collecting and cataloging LiDAR datasets from official sources. Metadata analysis was performed to categorize the data based on resolution, acquisition date, and geographic reference system. A structured database was created to store all relevant information, facilitating organized data management. To automate and expedite the acquisition process, customized scripts were developed and run in a Linux environment, allowing downloading the data directly from official websites, extracting the compressed files, and identifying the corresponding reference systems. The most common geographic reference systems encountered were WGS84 (EPSG 4326) and ETRS89 (EPSG 4258). Figure 1 shows the number of tiles and the corresponding EPSG for the MEES data. Note that, typically, a LiDAR tile at 1 m resolution contains 1,000,000 grid cells. Knowledge of the reference system of each piece of data allows assigning EPSG codes, and setting up corresponding GRASS GIS [12], [13] locations and mapset to collect and process them. A test area within the Emilia-Romagna region was selected as a representative sample, due to its varied topography and widespread LiDAR coverage. This region featured a mix of MEES and regionally acquired LiDAR data, making it an ideal environment for validating the merging procedure.

2) Data processing and merging

The next phase focused on merging and standardizing the collected data. The first step involved projecting the data into a common reference system. Since various datasets had different geographic reference systems, all data were projected into Italy Zone EPSG:6875 [14]. A new GRASS GIS location was set up for this purpose, and separate map sets were generated for each region to store the projected LiDAR data. A few GRASS GIS scripts were

Figure 1. LiDAR tiles available for this study, with the corresponding EPSG reference system codes. Data split by administrative region or province.

Figure 2. Spatial analysis of a sample area in Emilia Romagna (Northern Italy): slope map from the DTM at 5-meter resolution. The black segment refers to the topographic profile of Figure 4.

Figure 3. Spatial analysis of a sample area in Emilia Romagna (Northern Italy): hill-shade. The black segment refers to the topographic profile of Figure 4.

developed to parallelize the processing of individual LiDAR tiles, expediting the merging process. In case of overlapping LiDAR datasets, the following prioritization strategy was implemented that favored the most recent dataset, between datasets with same resolution. Gaps in LiDAR coverage were filled with TINITALY data. To further improve data consistency, smoothing algorithms [1] were applied to reduce abrupt elevation changes between overlapping datasets. Additionally, TINITALY was interpolated to a 5 m resolution to match the high-resolution LiDAR mosaic. A crucial step in the merging process involved

Figure 4. Topographic profile. Key: elevation data from TINITALY (red line), and HR-DTM (blue line). For profile location, cf. Figures 2 and 3.

Figure 5. Topographic profile. Key: elevation data from TINITALY (red line); HR-DTM (blue line); LiDAR data (green line). The inset zooms on the transition zone between LiDAR and TINITALY data, showing the smoothing effect in the HR-DTM, with respect to the original datasets.

adjusting elevation discrepancies. The mean elevation difference between TINITALY and the LiDAR-derived mosaic were computed, and the LiDAR mosaic was accordingly adjusted to align with TINITALY's baseline elevation. This correction was necessary to ensure seamless integration between the datasets. The final high-resolution DTM was obtained by merging the corrected LiDAR mosaic with the resampled TINITALY DEM at a 5 m resolution.

3) Preliminary quality control

The final step of the procedure consists of a thorough validation and quality control process to assess the accuracy and coherence of the merged dataset. Spatial analysis tools helped verifying discrepancies and discontinuities were reduced to a minimum. Preliminary quality control checks confirmed that the merging procedure significantly reduced inconsistencies in elevation data, as shown for a sample area in Figures 2, 3, and 4. More in detail, the *slope* of the sample area obtained from the DTM at 5 m resolution is shown in Figure 2, with gentle slopes

prevailing in a hilly river-plain sector. In Figure 3, the *hill shade* of the same area allows to appreciate the meandering pattern of the water courses, and the borders of terraced sectors. Figure 4 shows the topographic profiles obtained from the TINITALY DTM at 10 m resolution, and the HR DTM at 5 m resolution.

Figure 5 shows an example of a topographic profile for a transition zone between LiDAR data and TINITALY data is shown. The figure 5 illustrates that the HR DTM coincides with the TINITALY data in the areas without LiDAR data (ends of the profile). In the middle part, both data types are available, and in HR DTM priority is given to LiDAR data. Smoothing techniques are applied in the transition zones. In the inset, the detail of the profiles for the different data types (TINITALY, LiDAR, HR DTM) in the transition zone indicated by the dashed box can be appreciated.

III. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The proposed methodology relies on a computing infrastructure based on open-source software. The use of Linux-based environments, GRASS GIS, and Bash scripting allows for a full exploitation of servers equipped with four CPUs with a total 96 computing cores, and 530 gigabytes of RAM, ensuring efficient parallel processing and automation. The adopted setup significantly reduces computational time, with respect to a serial code, and enhances scalability, potentially allowing for progressive integration of new LiDAR data.

A major challenge in creating a high-resolution DTM for Italy is the fragmentation and uneven distribution of LiDAR datasets. Unlike centralized repositories, multiple regional and national institutions manage Italian LiDAR data, characterized by different acquisition times, formats, and coverages, hindering data integration. Nevertheless, the structured database presented here was designed for efficient updates, allowing seamless incorporation of new LiDAR datasets, and ensuring the DTM remains current and comprehensive.

The choice of 5-meter resolution represents a compromise between available high-resolution LiDAR (1-2 m) and coarser TINITALY (10 m) datasets. Whereas resampling TINITALY is not a conventional approach, it resulted in a limited impact, according to random sample tests. Most areas where LiDAR is not available are, in fact, in steep mountainous regions, where interpolation errors are acceptable. Therefore, the result is a spatially homogeneous DTM, enabling large-scale applications at high resolution.

The methodology outlined here ensures obtaining an accurate and comprehensive HR DTM, by leveraging high-resolution LiDAR data and compensating gaps with TINITALY data. The results demonstrated the effectiveness of the adopted approach in producing a seamless, high-resolution DTM for the Italian territory. By integrating cutting-edge computational resources, a

scalable database, and a balanced resolution strategy, the obtained DTM is flexible, updatable, and accurate, and may be employed in diverse fields of application, from hydrological and slope stability modeling to environmental planning.

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